

USAGE OF DISCOURSE ANALYSIS IN VARIOUS DISCIPLINE.

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Abstract: Language is a social phenomenon. The mother tongue of every nation living in the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan is a bright indicator of its national identity and spiritual culture. Language forms the mind in conjunction with thought. The connection between speech and thinking is manifested not only at the deep stages of psychological processing, but also at the level of social phenomena. The influence of words on a person and his behavior is well known to everyone. "Although language and thinking cannot live without each other, they do not represent the same phenomenon. This article provides information on the use of speech analysis in various disciplines.

Key words: Psycholinguistic literature, speech activity, national languages, emotion, bilingualism.

Thought is the culmination of objective existence, and language is a method of expression, a means of imparting and reinforcing ideas to other people. Words and concepts require each other dialogically. Currently, there are two principles in the interaction between languages in our country: on the one hand, the further development and improvement of national languages, and on the other hand, the importance of the Uzbek language as a state language is increasing. The independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the economic needs made it necessary to learn the Uzbek language, which is the mother tongue of a large number of people in the country, as the state language, which is of great social importance in the conditions of a multi-ethnic society. is enough.

Discourse analysis is defined "as a discursive formation in which the structures of sayability prompt the language of critical intervention with a much greater probability than in mainstream scholarship". There are many concepts and definitions associated with the word discourse. Chilton defined it as 'the use of language' in any form of communication such as written, spoken, or sign language. The language plays an important role in communicating or transferring messages and knowledge across society, time, culture, and customs. For example, signs have played an important role in communicating socio-cultural practices of ancient Egyptians. Archaeologists and philologist use ancient and primitive written or sign languages to identify social practices, history, culture, customs, social norms, traditions, and other such information about the old civilizations and other societies. Van Dijk exemplifies the scope of

discourse analysis as the use of written, spoken, and printed language to analyse the impact and role of texts or language in society through media communication, language and content of news, reports, journalism, political speech, advertisement, the language of war, criticism, and other such uses of language in the society in various disciplines.

According to the psycholinguistic literature, true bilingualism develops only when a person is able to express any idea in at least one language. If the speech is not fully formed in any language, then the structure of thought is distorted and the desire to express one's opinion fails, which not only leads to psychological oppression, but also to serious losses as communication and damage to the human personality. will bring. Such a phenomenon called semi-lingualism is very dangerous for society as a whole, because a certain part of its members cannot control their emotions and can't put their feelings, needs, and desires into words. If a person cannot say what he wants, he will not be able to compete equally with others, use the usual forms of communication, and he will have to resort to some other form of self-control, sometimes violence and force. Based on this, it is necessary to properly organize the correction of speech development of an individual from an early age. "Early Start" has a positive effect on the acceptance of the mother tongue and the subsequent acquisition of any other language "The earlier the language is acquired, the easier and more complete knowledge is acquired". it is necessary to use different situations. In such situations, an adult person sincerely expresses his feelings, shows the child ways to express both positive and negative emotions. In organized joint actions, the pedagogue is happy with the successes achieved by each child allows the child to have fun, supports and encourages every independent effort of the child, helps the child without noticing when he is in trouble, and at the same time refrains from giving him negative evaluations. affects their interactions with others, and this can create an emotionally uncomfortable environment in the group. It is necessary for an adult to make a child interested in himself, to participate in joint activities and games. For this purpose, he adds situations taken from his favorite fairy tales, fiction, and poems to the game situations. In such a meaningful communication with children, a relationship based on trust begins to form between them and the educator, and children have a desire to imitate him.

Visual arts, festivals and performances are used in preschool education as an important means of speech development. Their value is that it creates positive emotions, which in turn affects the level of language acquisition. The feeling of joy, excitement, excitement, anticipation of something unusual increases the child's receptiveness, strengthens the memorization of the material, affects the expressiveness of children's speech. Children ask a lot of questions while looking at pictures and works of art, and

they are eager to share their impressions with others. Children communicate with their pedagogues throughout the day in training, games, household and labor activities. The possibilities of developing a speech environment in pre-school education will depend entirely on the quality of the teacher's speech. Speech education of preschool children consists of three interrelated areas. The child acquires the grammatical system of the language on the basis of the development of knowledge in integral connection with the acquisition of object movement. The formation of the grammatical system of preschool children's speech is based on morphology (changing the word according to stems, numbers, agreements), word formation (using special tools to form another word based on one word), syntax (simple and complex includes work on creating a joint sentence). The pedagogue should first of all manage children's grammatical development through communication activities with the child himself (in the form of a dialogue) and with other children. The formation of the grammatical system in children - syntax, morphology, word formation - has its own special features, and the pedagogue needs to use various tools to develop them.

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